

2-Thioorotic Acid (Pyridinium Salt) as a New Spectrophotometric Reagent for Copper(II) Determination

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2-Thioorotic acid (pyridinium salt) has been used as a new reagent for direct spectrophotometric determination of Cu^{II} in mixed aqueous-organic solvent at pH 7 and below 60°. Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Fe^{II} and Fe^{III} have been found to interfere colorimetrically, and Ag^I, Al^{III} and Cr^{III} form precipitates in the general procedure.

Copper(II) and 2-thioorotic acid (6-hydroxy-2-mercaptopyrimidine-2-carboxylic acid) in pyridine medium, form an intensely green complex (Cu(C₅H₂N₂O₃S)(C₅H₅N)(H₂O)¹ in about 10 min and is stable for 48 h. Copper is estimated in the range 1.5–3.0 mg/100 ml with corresponding error of 1.00–0.66%. The method is suitable in absence of interfering ions. The method has been found to be applicable in the estimation of Cu^{II} in the waste liquor from a Cu-wire treatment industry. The result reasonably agrees with that obtained by atomic adsorption method.

Experimental

2-Thioorotic acid-2-thioorotic acid (C₅H₄O₃N₂S) was synthesised by the reported method² by subjecting 2-thiouracyl-4-aldehyde to Cannizaro's reaction. A 0.02 M solution of the reagent (98.8%) was prepared in 100 ml of a solvent mixture of pyridine-ethanol-water (75 : 20 : 5, v/v). Aqueous solution of cupric sulphate 0.5 mg Cu/ml was used.

Procedure : Aliquots of Cu^{II} solution containing 1.5–3.0 mg of Cu^{II} were treated with equal volume

of the reagent solution, and the mixture was diluted to 100 ml using the same solvent mixture and allowed to stand for 10 min. The absorbance were measured at 660 nm using a Systronics 103 spectrophotometer. A calibration graph was also prepared.

In three different experiments, each with a set of five, containing 1.5, 2.4 and 3.0 mg (100 ml) of Cu^{II}, the standard deviation values were respectively 0.0022, 0.0013 and 0.0045. The molar absorptivity and the Sandell's sensitivity were found to be $1.04 \times 10^2 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.6240 \text{ } \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively.

Effect of pH and diverse ions : The complex was found to be stable upto the 60° beyond which it decomposes into insoluble products. The complex was found to be stable at pH 7.5–5.0 below which it transformed into insoluble products. The complex, after its formation could be diluted to 1 : 1 with water without change in its properties. Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Fe^{II} and Fe^{III} formed coloured complexes, and Ag^I, Al^{III}, Pb^{II} and Cr^{III} formed precipitates under the conditions of the general procedure and therefore, must be absent.

Application : Homogenised sample of pickle liquor discharged from a copper wire treatment plant (Bhilai Wires Limited, Bhilai) was found to have pH \approx 0.35 and iron 24 mg dm^{-3} and copper 988 mg dm^{-3} (AAS method); other metals were not detectable. For estimation of Cu^{II} in this waste liquor, iron in aliquots (5 ml) was removed as

hydrated oxide (1 : 10 ammonia). The filtrate after removal of excess ammonia was adjusted to pH ~ 7 (dilute H₂SO₄), treated with 2-thioorotic acid (pyridine salt 0.02M; 5 ml) and adjusted to a definite volume by the diluent solutions. After 10 min, the absorbance was measured at 660 nm and the Cu^{II} content was determined from the calibration curve. A mean value of 985 mg dm⁻³ was obtained from three experiments.

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References

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